

Medical and social aspects of the prevalence of marital injuries among preschool children

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Annotation: Today, in many countries of the world, in the era of rapid technological development in all areas, injuries, especially among preschool children, are an extremely important and global problem for any country and for its health system. Especially in countries with a relatively high birth rate, household injuries among children, more precisely, among children of preschool age, are one of the most pressing medical and social problems. The urgency of the problem is that children of preschool age are injured not only in kindergartens, on the street, on playgrounds, but most of them (70%) are at home. These include falling from a window, drowning, suffocation, burns, poisoning and car accidents. In order to reduce injuries among children of preschool age, it was emphasized that it is important not only to strictly follow the established rules and norms, but also to activate the joint actions of teachers, educators and parents.

Keywords: family trauma, children, preschool age, problem, morbidity, disability and mortality, degree, indicator, fracture, burn.

The relevance of the topic The significant increase of injuries in life and the cases of disability and death caused by them, especially among children of preschool age in recent years, remains a huge global medical and social problem in any society.

Injuries among children, especially children of preschool age, are one of the most important and urgent leading medical and social problems today, and the increase in morbidity, disability and mortality among children and its occurrence, especially in children under 3-4 years of age the behavior of children as a result of their unconscious interest in the environment and parents' neglect of the risk factors observed in such aspirations in children are highly characterized.

The main goal of the research is to study and evaluate the prevalence of marital injuries among children of preschool age and its main reasons based on the study and analysis of demographic and statistical data.

Materials and methods

In the countries of the world, including our Republic, in the following years, the injuries that occur in children, including children of preschool age, in the living conditions and their complications, the literature and statistical data directed to the scientific study of comprehensive complex medical and social aspects. In the process of study and analysis, mainly the descriptive method was widely used.

Results and discussion

According to the authors, 20.2% of those hospitalized with injuries in 2010-2014 were children of preschool age, that is, 0-7 years old. It is noteworthy that the number of hospitalized patients increased

by 20% in 2014 compared to 2010. It is noted that 41% of the treated patients had fractures in the hands, 22.9% had fractures in different parts of the body, and 12.3% had fractures in the legs.

Ensuring children's health and well-being is one of the main and extremely important criteria in any society and in the future.

Ensuring children's health and well-being in any society is considered one of the main and extremely important criteria, and in the future it serves as its fundamental basis, which ensures reproductive health and the health of labor resources. [3] According to the results of scientific studies conducted in the city of Ufa, Russia, in 2003-2021, almost the majority of diseases among children aged 5-7 years, including injuries and poisonings, have been reduced by 81% [4] Binkbarin, the population of the city of Ufa even if it takes the second place after Kazan in Russia in terms of natural growth. According to the report of the World Health Organization "On the prevention of injuries in children in Europe", injuries are the main cause of death and disability in children in Europe, and the issue of reducing them is shown to be of medical and social importance in many cases. [4,20] According to the author, daily 12-78 injuries among children in the city of Ryazan. Its prevalence in the city of Ryazan is 149 per 100 children (139/1000 in Russia), which is higher than the general indicator of Russia. It is worth noting that the number of injuries is 1.5 times higher in boys. The number of injuries is higher in 1-3 and 12-14 years. During 2016-2020, an increase in injuries was observed in the region a significant number of life-threatening injuries to children, especially preschoolers, are related to road traffic accidents. Traffic accidents involving children are one of the leading causes of observed death in children. According to statistics, in 10 months of 2022, a total of 13,680 car accidents involving children were recorded in Russia. As a result, 14,921 children were injured and 484 teenagers died [7]

According to the studies conducted by R.D. Daudova, E.M. Bogatireva (2018) [8] in the Republic of Dagestan, the number of injuries caused by car accidents among adults was equal to 25.35.7 per 100,000 population. In such cases, it is noted that the main causes of death are not children crossing the road from unmarked places and drivers not following the rules of the road, but the lack of provision of necessary specialized emergency medical care for injured children. The analysis of injuries by the age of children showed that 26.7% of injuries occurring to children in motor vehicles correspond to children of preschool age, that is, 3-7 years old. It was determined that in the pre-school age, that is, 1-3 years old, this indicator makes up 15% of all children's injuries. Among newborns and children under one year of age, it was 0.9 is recorded. the main share of children's injuries is related to street and family injuries. Pustovoytova O.V., Shepilova R.I. and according to their data (2020), in 2018, there were more than 20,000 car accidents involving minors, which increased by 1.8% compared to 2018. According to the authors, pedagogues and educators have two tasks in order to form the rules of the road in children of preschool age. First of all, it is educational, i.e. what is the road and its crossings, road signs, as well as rules of conduct and educational, i.e. the safety of road users, drivers and pedestrians. is to form mutual respect for each other.

As a result, it is emphasized that the children first have knowledge about the rules of the road, the ability to correctly assess the situation on the road and to recognize the danger factor in advance. [13]. According to the data, in 2011 in Voronezh region, a total of 365 car accidents involving children took place, and as a result, 395 children were injured and 15 children died. Among children of all ages, more boys are affected, especially children of preschool age, and the difference is 1.5-2 times higher. [14]

According to many studied literatures, one of the main directions in improving the prevention of injuries and complications caused by traffic accidents among preschool children is to educate children at an early age, in preschool educational institutions. It is considered to carry out educational work at the level of current demand on the basis of special programs in cooperation with educators and parents. Among the injuries that occur among children, one of the most important and complex problems in any society, in practical health care and social protection issues, in prevention and treatment issues, and in theoretical and clinical medicine, is thermal burns in children. It is counted. According to WHO data, 12-20% of all injuries in the world are caused by burns, and on average 8% of them are caused by domestic injuries that occur in children. In the city of Kursk, I.A. Zarina, I.M. Razdorskaya and Budar (2008) [14] found that almost 60-65% of burns occur in children aged 0-7 years, and it was noted that boys have higher burn injuries in all age groups. Even children aged 1-3 A.A. Alekseva et al. (2005) noted that more than 70% of burns in Russia are hospitalized with burns of the II-III A degree, and most of them are children. It is noted that 65-80% of them are caused by hot liquids, 25.9% by heat, and 11.3% by electric burns in areas with high production. [14] Thermal burns in children account for 10% to 50% of all injuries in life. According to WHO and the UN Children's Fund, thermal burns in children are the third most common injuries after car accidents and drowning. The death rate in Russia is 1.2%. In children under one year of age, burns with hot food and hot water are high, and 92.1% of the main burns were caused by catching hot objects in 5.1% of cases. It was found that children of 4-5 years are more likely to burn in fire and this situation is 35%..

According to the author, the majority of burns were observed in urban children (70.5%), especially among preschoolers (75%). According to the causes, 98.3% were thermal burns. [18, 19] Studies conducted in the city of St. Petersburg showed that 85% of injured children were treated in outpatient and 15% in specialized inpatients. The prevalence of the injury is reported to be 130-150 per 1,000 population, and traditionally, boys have a higher incidence and a more severe course. A.G. Baidurashvili, S.V. Vissarionov and others show that more than 900 children are treated annually in the burn center operating in St. Petersburg, and more than half of them are under 2 years old. There are children. It is noted that the main causes of burns are 70% hot water, 4.5% fire, and 3% electrical burns. It is important to note that 40% of children with burns are deep, and the area of the burn is from 20% to 80% of the skin surface. According to the scientific conclusions of V.B. Rondyrev, E.A. Krasnova (2021) [23], marital trauma among children, especially children of preschool age, remains one of the most serious and urgent medical and social issues today, which reduction and prevention is considered one of the main tasks of the entire society in any country. Its complete solution can be achieved only through a comprehensive approach to the problem. The reason is that injuries among children are characteristic of their youth. The main causes of injuries in children under the age of seven are due to the neglect of their parents and the adults around them, while over the age of seven, many jokes, dangerous games, and lack of experience in dealing with children in the family occur without experience. According to the authors, prevention of injury among preschool children should be carried out in three directions, that is, individual, group and public. In this, the most important tasks should be, firstly, to eliminate the risk of getting injured, and secondly, to educate and train children in the prevention of injuries in a systematic way.

Conclusions

1. It became known from the studied literature that injuries in marriage, more precisely, injuries, disability and death among children due to injuries in marriage cause society not only social, demographic, medical, but also a large amount of economic, spiritual- brings spiritual.
2. In most literature, it is noted that there is a decrease in marital injuries among children of preschool age, and a relative increase is observed in some large cities. Most of the carried out scientific research works were carried out in far abroad and CIS countries, more precisely in the country of Russia.
3. Due to the fact that in our country, especially in the regions, especially in the case of Khorezm region, such scientific researches are almost not carried out, it is necessary to study the medical and social aspect of the causes of disability and death, as well as the measures to reduce it, from a scientific point of view. requires learning.
4. According to the results of carried out scientific research, among children of preschool age, especially between the ages of 1-4, foreign objects are stuck in the upper parts of the respiratory and digestive systems, burns, falling from above, injuries related to falls, etc. A relatively high prevalence of injuries is noted.

References

1. Baidurashvili A.G., Shapiro K.I. et al. The status and some problems of the organization of hospital medical care for children with trauma of the musculoskeletal system in St. Petersburg // Orthopedics, traumatology and rehabilitative surgery of childhood.-2016.-Tom 4.- Release 2.- Page 45-52.

2. Albitsky V.Y., Zelinskaya D.I. etc. Children's morbidity and disability // Russian Pediatric Journal. - 2008.- Number one.-P. 32-39.
3. Bashirova G.I., Malievsky V.A. Health status of children 5-7 years of age attending preschool educational institutions // Russian Pediatric Journal.- 2014. - Number one.-P. 30-33.
4. Filimonova E.I. Problem of child injury in Ryazan //Abstracts Nationwide scientific forum of students with international participation «STUDENT SCIENCE» – 2021.-p. 974.
5. Hanova T.G. Features of the education of safe behavior skills in the everyday life of senior preschoolers // Karelian scientific journal.- 2020.-No. 3 (32).-P.18-21.
6. Moshkin V. Cultivation of a culture of personal safety // Basics of safety of life.-2016.- No. 8.-P.13-16.
7. Kovalchuk V.A. Problem of prevention of child traffic injuries in conditions of extensive development of means of individual mobility on the road // Juristo-Pravoveda.-2022.-№4 (103).-P. 192-197.
8. R.D.Daudova, E.M.Bogatyreva Child injuries in Dagestan // Pediatrist.-2018.-T.9.- Release.3.-P. 34-40.
9. Pustovytova O.V., Shepilova N.I. Formation of knowledge about traffic rules in older preschool children // Perspectives of Science and Education.-2020.-№1 (43).- From 119-133.
10. Dedov A.A., Tsomiya V.V., Ilushina L.N. Medical and demographic characteristics of children affected in the traffic accident in Voronezh Oblast // Russian Medical and Biological Bulletin by the academician I.P.Pavlov.-2013.- Number one.-P.94-100.
11. Ulyanova L.V., Zazzdravnsh I.I. and others. Prevention of child transport trauma through the use of an interactive poster in the organized educational activities of older preschool children // Interactive Science.-2023.-№3 (79).-P.41-42.
12. Basova T.B., Olhova E.V. and others. Formation of safe vision skills of preschool children in the road-transport environment: Problems and perspectives // Modern science.-2022.- No. 3.- pp. 63-66.
13. Zarina I.A., Razdorskaya I.M. and others. Medical and social aspects of burn injury in children // Journal of scientific articles "Talent and education in the twenty-first century".-2008.- No. 3.-P.449-450.
14. Mirzagaliyev D.M., Avdeyev I.A. and others. Burns in children // Eurasian scientific journal.-2018.- No. 12.-P.268-270.
15. Axelrov M.A., Razin M.P. and others Medical and social aspects of thermal injury in children // Vyatsky Medical Bulletin.-2015.- Number four.- pp. 32-34.
16. Zakirov T.Sh., Yirkulov A.J. and others. Anesthesia in young children with critical burns // Electronic scientific journal "Biology and Integrative Medicine".-2019.-No. 10 (38). P.71-76.
17. Varganov M.V., Miklichev A.A. and others. The case of successful cure of a child with deep burns of the bones of the skull // Volga Scientific Bulletin.-2015.-No. 12-1 (52).-P.115-121.
18. R.R.Ganiyeva, A.P.Hilyazov and others. Epidemiology of burn injuries in children // Forms of young scientists.-2019.-No. 3 () 31.-S.256-261.
19. Sakharov S.P. Epidemiology of child burn trauma // Children's surgery.-2013.- Number two.-P.29-31.

20. Ibrahimova E.E. Methodological approaches to the formation of skills of safe behavior of pupils of educational institutions // Problems of modern pedagogical education.-2023.-No.79-4.- P.150152.
- 21.Solovyeva K.S., Zaletina A.V. Trauma of the child population of Chsant Petersburg // Orthopedics, traumatology and rehabilitative surgery of childhood.- 2016.- Tom 5.- Release 3.-S43-48.
22. A. G. Baindurashvili, S. V. Visarionov and others. Child injury and specialized care for children in a metropolis (on the example of St. Petersburg).- Russian newspaper.- 2018.-T.VIII.-2.-C.16-23.
23. Rondyrev V.B., Krasnova E.A. Prevention of child injuries // National Association of Scientists (NAU).- 2021.- No. 65.-P.31-33.
- 24.Sultanovna O. A. Traumatism Among The Population and Children, Medical and Social Aspects //Scholastic: Journal of Natural and Medical Education. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 24-30.
25. Omanova , A. .,& Abdullaev , I. . (2022). INJURIES AMONG CHILDREN AND SOME PECULIARITIES OF ITS SPREAD. (LITERATURE REVIEW). Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук, 2(6), 217–222. извлечено от <https://www.incademy.uz/index.php/EJMNS/article/view/2532>